

I. The Development of the *Women Film Pioneers Project* and its Role in Shaping Feminist Film Historiography

Interview with Jane Gaines

In the early 1990s, renowned film scholar Jane Gaines founded the *Women Film Pioneers Project* (WFPP). In this interview, she reflects on the impact of the WFPP on her own research at the intersection of empirical approaches and speculative historiography. Drawing on the term "unhistoricized women film pioneers", she talks about invisible aspects of film historiography and how the WFPP addresses these gaps by drawing attention to the diverse careers of women in early cinema. Gaines outlines the organizational structure of the WFPP, including the importance of technical support from *Columbia University* and the international collaborations with students and scholars. She emphasizes the WFPP's role in shaping feminist film historiography by focusing on outreach and recognition of marginalized filmmakers.

The interview is part of an interview series initiated by the research group „Aesthetics of Access. Visualizing Research Data on Women in Film History“ (DAVIF) (2021–2025), funded by the *German Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space* (BMFTR). The goal of the research group is to explore data visualizations in order to tell different stories differently. The WFPP is one of the film historiographical project partners, in addition to the *DFF – Deutsches Filminstitut & Filmmuseum* (DFF), both of whom have provided their research data for data visualizations.

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The interview was conducted by Pauline Junginger in February 2023.

Pauline Junginger

Could you tell me something about the beginnings of the *Women Film Pioneers Project* (WFPP)¹?

Jane Gaines

What is interesting about the history of the *Women Film Pioneers Project* is that it represents a moment in the transition from book volumes to online resources. And it is a perfect example of how the transition worked, almost by accident, in the years 2007 to around 2009. Think of it this way: Because the project was first envisioned as a multi-volume book set, to accommodate profiles on the number of women working in the new national film industries between 1896 and 1932, the volumes would have to have been gigantic in size and multiple in number. The first volume was supposed to have covered the US and Latin America. We had a second volume planned, which was to have covered Europe. But then we were discovering women who were working in the motion picture industry in China and India in the first two decades, all the way into the 1930s, which was still the silent era in those parts of the world, and so we planned to have a third volume. The volume dilemma became even more perplexing as scholars were calling our attention to women in Egypt, Tunisia, and Czechoslovakia working in these early film industries. There would be no way to quickly add to the three projected volumes – we had completely underestimated the number of women who were instrumental in founding national industries in a range of capacities, not just as actresses. The question of multiple volumes came to a head as I was moving from *Duke University* to *Columbia University*. Students working with me at Columbia were helping to compile the manuscript for the *Volume 1* publication and they thought it was strange that when we put together the paper copy to mail to the press, the manuscript was three feet high. When the huge manuscript arrived at the *University of Illinois Press*, they just let it sit because they weren't sure what to do with it.

It was actually at the suggestion of Joan Catapano, our first *Illinois* editor, that we began to think about online publishing, which was new at that time. It was our luck that *Columbia Libraries* was pioneering a digital publishing project, and they wanted us to be a pilot project for this "future of publishing" initiative. Around 2008 the first director Rebecca Kennison and her computer specialists looked at the copy – which we didn't refer to then as data – and what interested them most were the lists of non-extant and extant film titles. Those included all *Federation of International Film Archives* (FIAF) in which prints were held along with formats and the number of reels. The computer team actually thought it would be possible to stream *all* of the referenced films, of which there were thousands, of course, in undetermined physical condition².

My point about the *Columbia* computer programmers, however, tells us something about the public understanding of the materiality of motion picture film as well as the function of a film archive. Film historians know that these 35 millimeter prints, spread over

¹ Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta: *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://wfpp.columbia.edu/>.

² Over a decade later, some of the extant titles listed have been located in the archives where they have been housed, digitally restored, and some even streamed on FIAF archive websites, often featured on the WFPP home page. Projects like the *Kino Lorber* "Cinema's First Nasty Women" and "Pioneers: First Women Filmmakers" DVD sets have spurred this effort.

the world in national archives from Beijing to Brussels, would cost an enormous fortune to first restore and then scan, not to mention the coordination such an international effort would entail. While we did not have print access and had to wait for Youtube uploads for moving image clips, what we did have were hundreds of glossy stills that had been collected from FIAF archives worldwide, all scanned at 300 dpi as well as scans of lantern advertising slides from Joe Yranski's private collection³. Yet these image materials were especially exciting for the computer design experts, who envisioned a visually exciting website at a time when non-profit websites were not known for their great graphics. Although *Illinois Press* liked the idea of innovating an online version, they couldn't have made it free, and it was becoming clear that we needed an open access solution.

As an international project, we were already making a commitment to Latin America, where, Irela Núñez, archivist at the *Cineteca Nazionale* in Rome had discovered Stefanía Socha⁴, a Polish immigrant to Peru who set up a theatrical training company in Lima where she was also making motion pictures. We were working on profiles and overview essays on Argentina, Mexico, and Brazil at the time and it made no sense to require a subscription for access or to be tied to books in English only. We committed around 2010 to the online project in part because we envisioned profiles in multiple languages, but in retrospect it seems strange that we didn't imagine Google Translate. So the *University of Illinois Press* dropped out but has maintained the book series *Women and Film History International*⁵. Since then, *Columbia University Libraries* has done all of the work to design and maintain the *Women Film Pioneers Project* also adding enhancements, like the links to Youtube for streamed clips in the development stage between 2010 and 2013, when the project was officially launched.

Pauline Junginger

What were the initial goals of the WFPP?

Jane Gaines

The question about the initial goals is interesting, because we had a big interest in doing historiographic work committed to an understanding of historiography as ever-expanding and contingent. This was before the conversations within digital humanities about "database histories." When you discover more, you change the story, and you keep rearranging the way that you research or explore archival materials. So the concept for the DAVIF research group's more recent *Women Film Pioneers Explorer*⁶ project corresponds exactly with one of our original goals. Yet we didn't use the word "explorer," which is so intriguing now, especially given the potentiality of digitally-enabled "searching." We also thought that the WFPP should be a teaching tool. And so we added long bibliographies and designed

³ I should note that between 2010 and 2013 we found few free scans of silent era posters or publicity stills on the Internet to meet our 300 dpi standard.

⁴ Mario Lucioni and Irela Núñez: "Stefanía Socha", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-kbh5-dy45>.

⁵ Woman and Film History International. A network of affiliated scholars, researchers, archivists, and film programmers dedicated to the study of women's Film History, <https://www.wfhi.org/>.

⁶ Henri Dickel, Matija Miskovic, Kharazm Noori, Christian Schmidt, Atefeh Soltanifard, Sarah-Mai Dang, and Thorsten Thormählen: "Women Film Pioneers Explorer", 2021, <https://www.online.uni-marburg.de/women-film-pioneers-explorer>.

connections to every FIAF archive through filmographies that included both extant and non-extant film titles. We were also thinking of the *Giornante del Cinema Muto* silent film festival in Pordenone, Italy. We wanted to encourage public screenings of extant titles – to disprove the prevalent idea that the films on which these women worked did not exist.

Our theoretical commitment was to prove that although earlier feminist film theory, as we know, has advanced the idea that there were “no women” and therefore that narrative cinema was always patriarchal cinema, we were finding that more and more actual women all over the world had been involved in the early stages of motion picture film production. They were not just actresses, but also did the publicity, the wardrobe, and sometimes undertook the camerawork. Women often edited, and many also wrote scenarios, beginning in the first decade when there were never enough stories to meet the demand. So at this juncture, our concern was, if we were expanding to so many national cinema cases, and wanted the WFPP to be a teaching tool, then we wanted students to continue the research. Therefore we started using the FIAF *Treasures from the Film Archives* database⁷ and imagining archival research even if, as yet, young scholars did not have the resources to travel.

However, some of the first students at *Columbia* who were using the FIAF *Treasures from the Film Archives* database as well as the *American Film Institute* online catalogue to make filmographies began to discover conflicting film title and credit data. So we added a box at the end of every filmography we originally named the “Credit Check,” but morphed into “Credit Report,” because we also realized that early cinema, in fact, all research, is subject to rediscovery and change. So the “Credit Report” box was a place where we could indicate that we weren't exactly certain of the credit information, but where variations could be listed and changes might later be made.

Another complication we had is that we realized how many of these women we were discovering were unknown, even in the film history field. So why would anyone search for them, unless that researcher had some kind of entry? In conversations with computer programmers we kept using the word “map,” which, for some reason, computer specialists resisted. Still, we were concerned with how people would find new information if they weren't led to it, that is, if we don't use some form of “bread crumbs.” So the overview essay was designed as a means of pulling in online content searchers, with links from names to profiles. In a very early discussion before the ubiquity of the hyperlink, I recall asking “What if readers don't click on the links?” The overview essay, however, soon took on a life of its own. The first essays were on screenwriters, exhibitors, editors and the first French colorists who worked in a factory in Vincennes owned by a mother and daughter. Later essays featured newspaper women, fan magazines in British culture, and most recently women in the Uruguayan silent film industry. We originally imagined one overview for every region, or nation.

Pauline Junginger

That's very interesting. Could you give us some examples?

⁷ FIAF Treasures from the Film Archives, <https://www.fiafnet.org/pages/Publications/Treasures-From-Film-Archives.html>, last accessed 06/23/2023.

Jane Gaines

For example, working with Italian film historians and co-editor Monica Dall'Asta, we discovered an unusual number of amazingly interesting cases, and I was surprised to find that in the Naples Region, Elvira Notari's⁸ *Dora Film Company* was not the only company with a woman's name – there were six others. Although we still don't have an overview for Italy, we have one for Latin America, which is probably important because one might not guess that there were so many Latin American women active in the early film industry. One of our favorite examples is actress-producer Mimí Derba⁹, who founded the *Azteca Films* company in Mexico City in 1917. The company stood up to the American exports that were dominating the Mexican market, and Derba is a *cause célèbre* because the company was part of nation building immediately following the Mexican Revolution.

It is the same case in India which started its film industry around the time of independence, although much later. In China in the 1920s, following the 1911 Republican Revolution overthrowing the Qing Dynasty, the national film industry began in Shanghai. So motion pictures have in so many cases been tied to nation-founding projects. And, again addressing your question of goals, one of the original ideas was the world feminist interest in researching the changing status of women as related to nationalist projects.

Another overview essay focuses on the "family mode" of production, for example, the Thanouser Company that innovated serials in New Rochelle, New York. And it was not just Edwin and Gertrude Thanouser but also other relatives who were part of the business. Now their grandson Ned has done restoration on the surviving Thanouser films. So it was an extended family that wrote, acted in, and produced those films and we have found more and more families worldwide who participated similarly in the early film industry.

Pauline Junginger

Could you elaborate a little on the challenges you were dealing with?

Jane Gaines

So the question for which the overview essay was one solution was how do we get young researchers engaged, to pull them in. From today's perspective, I think it's kind of fascinating that the project began only a decade ago, and I was working with Maria Fosheim Lund, Diana Wade, Julie Buck, Katy Grey, and Kate Saccone, the remarkable young scholars who worked as the first WFPP coordinators, which meant supervising other graduate students and reaching out to scholars and archivists originally according to language groups – Spanish, French, German, Italian, and later mostly Chinese and even Japanese¹⁰.

Another challenge we faced when we thought about how to make new information easily accessible had to do with "searchability." While it was comparatively easy to set up searches by geography or occupation, as an innovative database we didn't have models to follow when it came to the question of the broad "searchability" that we now take for

⁸ Kim Tomadjoglou: "Elvira Notari", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-zdmp-rs37>.

⁹ Angel Miquel: "Mimí Derba", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-pw36-1k24>.

¹⁰ Here, I'm thinking of the 2016 conference we held at *Columbia* on Chinese American Esther Eng that brought Hong Kong scholar Louisa Wei and her film and featured the discovery of Japanese director Tazuko Sakane.

granted. We consulted with the *Columbia* metadata librarian who advised us to give our writers a list of occupation terms before they began writing. Of course we realized that terminological consistency would make searching easier. But what is now clear a decade later in the *Women Film Pioneers Explorer* visualizations is the incredible range of names and titles and types of occupations that we never dreamed existed when we first began, for instance – agent, accountant, censor, projectionist, and exhibitor, not to mention all of the on-set jobs like lighting designer and camera operator. Women were investors and theater owners but also maintenance workers. And this range raises new issues I think we all need to write about, because we knew we didn't want online resources to encourage what could later be called "paint by number" history. There may be a degree to which world cinema history is a version of what I mean by this – matching terms to find consistent patterns when language and culture differences mean that "given" terms don't fit in such a range of cases. Needless to say, we never circulated a list of occupations.

Pauline Junginger

What is striking about the WFPP is the abundance of visual material. Could you describe the process of making a digital project of all the material you had gathered for the book volumes?

Jane Gaines

When our computer team designed the platform, they included ovals for portraits of the pioneers. But while they imagined that we would be able to "fill" these ovals with portraits, we knew that there would be many empty ovals because no portrait could be found. We had hundreds of glossy stills, mostly bought from the *Academy of Motion Picture Arts and Sciences* Library in Beverly Hills, which is a very rich repository. Some portrait stills came from the *Billy Rose Theatre Division of The New York Public Library* and the *Museum of Modern Art Stills* library before it was closed to researchers. Others came from the *British Film Institute*, the *Swedish Film Institute*, the *Cinémathèque Royale de Belgique*, the *Cinémathèque Française*, and many we have yet to use online came from the *Deutsche Kinemathek*, as well as the East German *Deutsche Film-Aktiengesellschaft*. The majority of the photographic portraits we uploaded had no circulation in published books and articles at the time, and a scholar had to travel to a film archive to access the company and performer files where they had been catalogued. I jump-started the stills collection by visiting a range of FIAF paper photographic archives in several countries and later researchers provided their own scanned images of frame enlargements, production stills, and portraits. It was a real bonanza when family members became involved as when Julie Buck tracked down a niece of Julia Crawford Ivers who contributed a rare photograph of the writer-director-producer whose portrait had virtually disappeared likely due to the fact that she had been a suspect in the William Desmond Taylor murder.

Pauline Junginger

So this means that there is also something like an analog archive?

Jane Gaines

Yes. And we will at some point deposit not just glossy stills but original death certificates, lobby cards, and in some cases passport photos donated by relatives in the *Columbia Libraries Special Collections*.

Pauline Junginger

That's very interesting! But where is it now?

Jane Gaines

We have filing cabinets in the corridor storing, for example, xerox copies of *Motion Picture World* articles that are alphabetized by figure, and I'm only mentioning this because young scholars may wonder how we managed before the resources of *Digital History Research Library* that has high resolution scans of the very issues of *Photoplay* that we once had to find by travelling to the *Wisconsin Historical Society* in Madison, Wisconsin, or the *Margaret Herrick Library* of the *Academy of Motion Picture Arts and Sciences* in Beverly Hills, California.

It should be noted, however, that in the WFPP we don't have portraits of every figure featured, to return to my earlier point. When the platform was designed, the computer specialists expected us to be able to find these online, which is completely ridiculous. They didn't understand the rarity of the images that we were finding in archives all over the world – one student even bringing them back from Kyoto, Japan, for instance. Or we bought rare Italian postcards like the one of Giulia Cassini-Rizzotto¹¹, for instance, or the double exposure of comedienne Flora Finch¹² found on eBay. A bizarre development I should mention is that now when you do a Google image search for any one of these figures by name, the overwhelming majority of the scanned photos that come up are from the *Women Film Pioneers Project*. In effect, the project has "populated" the Internet with early film images of women who were occupation pioneers in addition to the many silent actress images uploaded to a plethora of sites on silent cinema. Basically, copyright is moot because these images are so early. However, when we get an image inquiry, we don't give permission, we refer inquiries to the source archive which is easy, because every image has a photo credit and all archive contact information is accessible via the Resources Menu¹³. If the image is from a personal collection, we might help with that.

Pauline Junginger

For the profiles you refer to Annette Förster's concept of the "professional itinerary" or "careerography". However, her book was only published in 2017. Was there a different model for the profiles in the beginning of WFPP?

Jane Gaines

The reference to Förster's "careerography" came because we had read her dissertation before she published the book.¹⁴ Annette was also an early contributor and she was a par-

¹¹ Alessandro Faccioli and Marzia Maino: "Giulia Cassini-Rizzotto", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-704d-n502>.

¹² April Miller: "Flora Finch", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-3etb-tk37>.

¹³ Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta: *Women Film Pioneers Project: Resources*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://wfpp.columbia.edu/resources/>.

ticipant in the first *Women and the Silent Screen* conference in Utrecht, the Netherlands. My recollection is that the profiles idea came as a reaction to the emphasis on the too few women who were standing in for the so many women – Alice Guy Blaché¹⁵ (France and the US), Lois Weber¹⁶ (the US), and Asta Nielsen¹⁷ (Denmark and Germany), for instance. Yet in retrospect, I'm kind of sorry that we emphasized careers so much, because when looking at jobs in the early film industry, women had many occupations such as wardrobe mistress that don't necessarily fit in the concept of careers. In the film industry, people with those low-level jobs are not mentioned in fan magazines or the trade press, but they can be found in payroll records, some of which exist, as I found in the *Cecil B. DeMille Collection* at *Brigham Young University* in Utah. So in our focus on careers we were inadvertently cutting out a lot of jobs and didn't find a way to consistently deal with the question of social class difference considering, for example, the kind of elite education that some of the U.S. writers had. For instance, prolific *Paramount* screenwriter Beulah Marie Dix¹⁸ was an honors graduate of the elite *Radcliffe College*, the women's college affiliated with Harvard University. While it may be that we have dealt with social class origins in the case of actress "rags to riches" stories, the possibilities for a class analysis is there in the WFPP data. I later considered the social class question in contrasting the privilege of famous screenwriter Frances Marion¹⁹ with the station of executive secretary Valeria Belletti²⁰ who dreamed of being a screenwriter. A good sign of interest is the fact that Erin Hill's book on industry secretaries, so perfectly titled *Never Done*,²¹ won the *Society for Cinema and Media Studies* best book award in 2018.

Pauline Junginger

Did I understand you correctly that today you feel that the concept of the career also makes things invisible? Are you thinking of changing the concept of the profiles?

Jane Gaines

I think that might be another phase, because right now it's difficult to do research on lower level workers like secretaries and maintenance workers because they remain "unnamed." Even the concept of the "extra" which refers to a day work performer doesn't neatly fit the current profiles model, and of course there were also temporary workers in the secretarial pool. Many of the current profiles, however, do deal with the irregularity of work for writers who in interviews referred to having to move regularly from studio to studio and job to

¹⁴ Annette Förster: *Women in the Silent Cinema: Histories of Fame and Fate*, Amsterdam University Press, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt1zqrmpg>.

¹⁵ Alison McMahan: "Alice Guy Blaché", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-5a4c-yq24>.

¹⁶ Shelley Stamp: "Lois Weber", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-zsv8-nf69>.

¹⁷ Julie Allen: "Asta Nielsen", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-dw7e-x721>.

¹⁸ Wendy Holliday: "Beulah Marie Dix", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-rr4x-p297>.

¹⁹ JoAnne Ruvoli: "Frances Marion", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-kvq5-gm17>.

²⁰ Valeria Belletti doesn't have an entry in the WFPP, but is mentioned in Frances Marion's profile.

²¹ Erin Hill: *Never Done: A History of Women's Work in Media Production*, New Brunswick, NJ: Rutgers University Press, 2016.

job. We might, however, deal with irregular workers and work conditions in a new segment we call "Projections."²² This section is meant for more experimental essays, especially those including clips which means that they are a type of what the field now calls video essay. I should add here, however, that I once wrote an essay titled "Anonymity: Uncredited and Unknown in Early Cinema"²³ which I intended as a reaction to the very name recognition on which the WFPP has depended, effectively a critique of the concept of "career profile."

Pauline Junginger

The next question is from my colleague Marlene Leonie Biebricher. In her dissertation project she focused on the list of so called "unhistoricized women film pioneers" from Germany from the WFPP website.²⁴ One problem with this list is that some of the women who are listed as "unhistoricized" are actually known in Germany and there is research on them in the German context. Yet, on the WFPP website they are framed as unhistoricized. So how do you come up with the lists of the "unhistoricized women film pioneers"?

Jane Gaines

In order to explain this term I have to go back in history a little. I was interested in researching women film pioneers because I'd spent the year 1993 at *Vassar College*, historically a US women's college. And I had this idea that we could get funding to compare women makers, that is, directors, with other women artists, for example painters. I thought about doing a comparative project on women photographers, women directors, and women artists. However, that project was never funded and it turned into the WFPP instead. Our initial focus on directors didn't take into account the complexity of the kinds of jobs women were doing, as we found when we continued. I invented the term "unhistoricized" because we had long lists of names and wanted to keep alive the hope that more would be discovered as a way of encouraging research. And then this term got picked up. The term "unhistoricized" was meant to refer to a group of women who "as yet" have not been fully researched and with the term we signal that there is interest in that research. The term doesn't refer to those who did not exist but rather to those for whom we have at least a name but about whom there is little to no *published* research. The German names on the list don't exactly fit because there may be research and publication in German, so in this case "unhistoricized" is more a way of keeping track of the figures we would like to see included in the WFPP inventory, and an easy solution might be to include a section of links to German publications so that one could use Google Translate to access that information.

I should mention here a fascinating development in the field of feminist film research to think about films that were never made. Whom will we never find? What films are lost? A collection that I contributed to titled *Incomplete: Feminist Possibilities of the Unfinished Film*, edited by Alix Beeston and Stefan Solomon²⁵ is based on the idea that many works made by women were never finished. In my article I focus on the story of Lule

²² Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta: *Women Film Pioneers Project: Projections*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://wfpp.columbia.edu/projections/>.

²³ Jane Gaines: "Anonymity: Uncredited and Unknown in Early Cinema", in: André Gaudreault, Nicolas Dulac, and Santiago Hidalgo (eds.): *A Companion to Early Cinema*, Malden, MA: Wiley-Blackwell, 2012.

²⁴ Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta: *Women Film Pioneers Project: Unhistoricized Women Film Pioneers*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://wfpp.columbia.edu/resources/unhistoricized-women-film-pioneers/>.

Warrenton.²⁶ She had started her own company called the All-Woman Company, but some of those films that were advertised appear to have never been shot or gone into production. So this is a particular problem in our field. And for me the "unhistoricized" question goes along with that idea of never made, never finished, never processed. It's a placeholder to stand in for "lost." What's interesting about the term is that in English "unhistoricized" could be either synonymous with "not known" or alternatively "unstoried."

Pauline Junginger

What is necessary to make the WFPP up and running? Who is working behind the scenes?

Jane Gaines

To get WFPP up and running we have technical people in the *Columbia University's Butler Library*. And Kate Saccone for many years did the detailed editing work. For the profiles we have a style sheet and for the overview essays we do peer reviews. We also get support from our *Film and Media Studies* MA program, which is very international. As I noted, whenever we admitted students fluent in Spanish, French, Italian or German, I would find them paid positions and have them work with scholars in those countries where they could work on the basis of a shared language. This explains why the WFPP is so diverse, but by diversity I mean that it was matching with student interest that produced research on African American, Hindi, and Mexican cinema figures which shifted to East Asia with a recent change in the student body. This new East Asian film history interest is reflected in the *Women and the Silent Screen* conference which Yiman Wang held in Shanghai in 2017 and we continued in what we called "Online China Time" Zoom segment in 2021 when we had to postpone the New York in-person *Women and the Silent Screen XI* conference because of COVID and scholars could not travel from China.

Pauline Junginger

Does the WFPP receive any funding or institutional support?

Jane Gaines

Besides the support from our MA in Film and Media Studies program, the main institutional support is coming from the *Columbia University Libraries*. We now, however, have an alumnus Dwight Cleveland, a mega film poster collector, who has endowed fellowships for graduate students to work on the WFPP, generously naming the fellowships after Frederica Sagor Maas²⁷, a silent era screenwriter who attended the *Teachers College* at *Columbia University* and was later Black-listed in the 1950s Red Scare.

²⁵ Alix Beeston and Stefan Solomon: *Incomplete: The Feminist Possibilities of the Unfinished Film*, Berkeley: University of California Press, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1525/9780520381483>.

²⁶ Jane Gaines: "Lule Warrenton", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-z5tw-7v92>.

²⁷ Radha Vatsal: "Frederica Sagor Maas", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-cn0j-rf56>.

Pauline Junginger

This year is the 10th anniversary of WFPP online: How did the WFPP as an online project influence the way that you are thinking about your research or about feminist film historiography in general?

Jane Gaines

The journal *Feminist Media Histories* has recently produced many issues around historiography, publishing recent issues from *Women and the Silent Screen* papers and another forthcoming on archives. In 2022, there was an issue on *Historical Speculation* for which I did an article that was a spin off from my book, *Pink-Slipped: What Happened to Women in the Silent Film Industries?*²⁸ In that article I titled "Counterfactual Speculation: What if Antonia Dickson Had Invented the Kinetoscope?"²⁹ I'm speculating that the talented sister invented the kinetoscope. Now the field largely agrees that her brother William K. L. Dickson invented the kinetoscope, not really Thomas Edison, his employer. Edison bank-rolled all of those experiments involved in inventing the kinetoscope, which was the prototype for the cinematograph. So in the WFPP, it didn't seem logical to give Antonia a career profile in the strict sense we were at one time using.

But that was also because at the time, I didn't know enough about her. I knew *History of the Kinetograph, Kinetoscope, and Kinetophone*,³⁰ which she is credited with co-authoring with her brother and published in 1895, and it should be called the first history of motion pictures. But as I started to think in my book *Pink-Slipped*, the problem of the women film pioneers was an empirical challenge to a theoretical position, that position being that there were "no women" in early cinema. But I am not an empirical historian, and in doing this research, it took me really 10 years to realize that the answer to the question as to what happened to women in the early film industries was not easy to answer definitively. Many many factors are involved. And so it was the question as to why we selectively research when we need some stories to be told over others that led me to read the philosophy of history. And *Pink-Slipped* was informed by the philosophy of history which led me to counterfactual speculation.

And what I tried to do with Antonia Dickson was to still do empirical research, but to do empirical research up to the point where you don't know anymore, you have exhausted available sources. And then, following Catherine Gallagher's work on the history of counterfactuality³¹ within the discipline of history, you create what she calls a "nexus," the point at which things diverge from accepted factuality. When I started doing more research on Antonia Dickson I discovered that she was a music genius, a performer who had a higher university degree than her brother. She went to Leipzig, Germany, to study piano and then, in London, she was admitted into the *Royal Academy of Organists*. So she was very talented. I realized that in order to write the 1895 *History of the Kinetograph, Kinetoscope, and Kinetophone*, she had to do an enormous amount of technical

²⁸ Jane Gaines: *Pink-Slipped: What Happened to Women in the Silent Film Industries?*, Champaign, IL: University of Illinois Press, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.5406/j.ctt212172p>.

²⁹ Jane Gaines: "Counterfactual Speculation: What if Antonia Dickson Had Invented the Kinetoscope?", in: *Feminist Media Histories*, 1 July 2022, 8 (3): 8–34. <https://doi.org/10.1525/fmh.2022.8.3.8>.

³⁰ William Kennedy Dickson and Antonia Dickson: *History of the Kinetograph, Kinetoscope and Kinetophone*, Museum of Modern Art, 1895.

³¹ Catherine Gallagher: *Telling It Like It Wasn't: The Counterfactual Imagination in History and Fiction*, Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226512556.001.0001>.

reading, including patent filings, for instance. And because her writing style is completely different from her brother's, it is clear that she did the writing. She also wrote, with her brother's name on it, an early biography of Thomas Edison published in 1895 also. So in this research I came to realize that there are unresolved issues around the synchronized kinetophonograph and the projecting motion picture and that she was likely more honest about progress on that invention than either her brother or Edison had been. Both men maintained that the kineto-phonograph had been invented, but it is now clear that this machine was never in sync. The point is that you can't claim it's a kineto-phonograph if you can't sync up the image with the sound. Antonia's other published accounts of the stakes in the invention were much more precise and didn't make these erroneous claims. She completely understood what the projecting kinoscope could do. So the "nexus" was the point at which William K. L. Dickson, her brother, quit Edison, ostensibly as a consequence of a dispute around his working with a competing team that was trying to invent the projecting kinoscope. And I argued, in the counterfactual speculative part, that she kept working on the projecting machine in their basement at home. After all, she was living with her brother and his wife, and continued to do so up until her death. And therefore, in the "counterfactual," she invented the "projecting" kinoscope. There are all kinds of interesting ways to challenge the established narrative history of invention. That was only one of them. So just to say, to give that as an example, the Antonia Dickson research is really a spin off from both the WFPP and *Pink-Slipped*.

Pauline Junginger

In your book *Pink-Slipped* you write that the relationship between the WFPP and your book is oblique. Could you explain this a little more?

Jane Gaines

Well, it was oblique in that I was finding so many different clues as to why each one of the "pioneers" couldn't continue their careers at some point. As a field, scholars pretty much agree that in many countries the film industry was becoming corporatized as a consequence of bank loans, in the U.S. beginning around 1916. This was professionalizing the industry to the degree that it was no longer a cottage industry, which is an aspect of the "family mode" of production. Before the professionalization these small companies needed women in every capacity. Also, there were personal issues like marital status and pregnancy that complicated each case. Let's not forget world politics. World War I, for instance, is relevant, because after 1914, Germany, Italy, the UK, and France could no longer compete and the US took over the world film market in 1917. The industries in those countries were decimated. So as in the case of Germany, women stepped into directing and producing because of the war when men left for the front. I also didn't want to continue to narrate the years after the end of the silent era in the US in which the industry comes in and men are completely taking over. Actually, that would have been kind of dreary. In the WFPP we want to suggest that there was a range of occupations held by women, proving that they were not just directors. We wanted to make the point that they worked in so many different ways, areas and occupations, and after women directors were pushed out, beginning in 1916, they remained longer in other occupations. However, at this juncture, the most important work to be done is cross-cultural given that the US

model of economic change pushing out women new to the work force and temporarily in positions of power – does not fit all – at all.

Pauline Junginger

Did you also think of other categories besides "countries" and "occupations" for your keywords at some point? For example, "institutions" would be interesting as a category because it would allow for researching the role of production companies.

Jane Gaines

Absolutely. There are two things I regret. Firstly, I regret that we didn't put the production companies in and secondly, we began by thinking that we had to restrict the word count, which was the consequence of thinking we would be publishing in paper. So, secondly, we cut off the theatrical careers of the earliest pioneers. And then we were really, really sorry, because when we held *Women and the Silent Screen* conference in 2022, we were realizing how many pioneers had two careers in New York, also working, at the same time, in the *New York Theater*. At the *New York Public Library* we had already begun to use the treasure trove of images of women who were active in both the theater and cinema around 1910–1920.

Pauline Junginger

I think it would be possible to still include the production companies, right?

Jane Gaines

It's a lot of work. The other aspect we don't want to forget is how much field expertise is required, and it's advanced film students who know the importance of production companies before the advent of *Netflix*. And in the beginning of the project, we were also working with contributors who were not necessarily silent cinema experts for whom company names did not figure significantly.

Pauline Junginger

So besides the theater careers that you've already mentioned, which other aspects were not included in the WFPP and thus were made invisible?

Jane Gaines

The other issue is about marital status. We made a list of partners and tried to foreground that marital status. We look forward, however, to the publication of a new dissertation on sexual abuse or what could be called #MeToo in the early US industry. In her research, Kelly McElroy even interviewed women who were still alive and who had worked in the early industry and decided to quit because of harassment. Also, we have all been very interested in gay, lesbian and bisexual lives. Julie Buck wrote a profile on bisexual Mary McLane³² and Don Crafton discovered distributor Edna Williams³³ who put her name together with that of her partner to form the *Ednella Export Corporation*, and we still know

³² Julie Buck: "Mary MacLane", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-krqp-yg59>.

³³ Donald Crafton: "Edna Williams", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-0gjb-wr23>.

of cases that need further research. Also, Kiki Loveday's essay *Do You Believe in Fairies*³⁴ on queer sexuality relative to Alice Guy Blache's *Le Fee aux Choux* (1900) points to even more exciting and innovative work to come, appearing in the new Projections section. The *Cinema's First Nasty Women* project has a presence on the *Women Film Pioneers Project* website and we partner with the *American Film Institute* "Women They Talk About" project³⁵ funded as a *National Endowment for the Humanities* Digital Humanities project.

Pauline Junginger

How would you describe the relationship between the Women and the Silent Screen (WSS) community and the WFPP?

Jane Gaines

The WFPP community and the WSS community is not necessarily the same as the original writers of WFPP profiles were scholars and archivists who regularly attended the *Le Giornante del Cinema Muto (Pordenone Silent Film Festival)* and are *Domitor*³⁶ members. We had trouble convincing writers in the very first years because they couldn't yet visualize what it was going to become before digital scholarship online exploded. Today, we have a backlog because another generation of film students conducts research largely online, and we get inquiries from people outside of the field who would like to write profiles. Most thrilling, however, is when relatives come out of the woodwork with material. The best story of all is about Marion E. Wong³⁷ who founded the *Mandarin Film Distribution Co. Ltd.* in Oakland, California. It is now well known that she directed, produced, and acted in *The Curse of the Quon Gwon: When the Far East Mingles with the West* in 1916. For years, however, silent film historians knew of only one article about her company published in the *Moving Picture World* in 1916. Then, a scholar from NYU found her nephew who gave us more information and they presented a joint paper at *Women and the Silent Screen Entr'acte* online in 2021. In 2022, just before the *Women and the Silent Screen XI* conference, Marion E. Wong's great grandson showed up in the MA architecture program at *Columbia*. He and his mother have written the most amazing family history with photographs and documents going back to the founding of the railroads which brought their ancestors from China to the US West Coast. Their family archive is the basis of a really wonderful family history which they are publishing in a forthcoming special issue of the *Journal of Chinese Cinemas* comprised of papers from the *Women and the Silent Screen XI* conference, and mother and son have titled the memoir *Marion Evelyn Hong before and after the Curse of the Quon Gwon (1916)*.³⁸

My point is that at the start of this project we did set the goal of recognition within official world cinema history, a goal that Shelley Stamp reminds us has yet to be realized. What we did not envision was local outreach. Our next project phase includes outreach to

³⁴ Kiki Loveday: "Do You Believe in Fairies? Cabbages, Victorian Memes, and the Birth of Cinema: Seeing Sapphic Sexuality in the Silent Era", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-f1sh-k143>.

³⁵ AFI Catalog: *Women They Talk About. Discovering America's Female Film Pioneers*, <https://aficatalog.afi.com/wtta/>, last accessed 03/26/2025.

³⁶ *Domitor* in an international society for the study of early cinema. It's an association for people with a scholarly interest in cinema from its beginnings to 1915. Further information: <https://domitor.org/>.

³⁷ Jenny Kwok Wah Lau: "Marion E. Wong", in: Jane Gaines, Radha Vatsal, and Monica Dall'Asta (eds.): *Women Film Pioneers Project*, New York, NY: Columbia University Libraries, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-s9yz-e287>.

Pauline Junginger: "The Development of the Women Film Pioneers Project and its Role in Shaping Feminist Film Historiography. Interview with Jane Gaines", in: Sarah-Mai Dang, Pauline Junginger, and Anne Hart (eds.): *Data Practices, Provenance, and Categorizations in Film History. Interviews with Scholars, Archivists, and Project Managers*, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17234308>.

the small US towns which these women left for work in bigger towns, to publish their stories in local print and online newspapers. Top on our list is Watseka, Illinois, from which circus performer Fern Andra³⁹ traveled to Berlin where in 1917 she founded the *Fern-Andra Film Company*. Now we also need to ask what small towns in Germany did young women leave to travel to Berlin with the hope of finding a job in a new industry.

Pauline Junginger

There is definitely still a lot to do! Thank you so much for this inspiring interview and the fascinating insights into the history of the WFPP.

³⁸ Lisa Kumaradjaja and Chris Kumaradjaja: "Marion Evelyn Hong before and after *the Curse of the Quon Gwon* (1916)", in: *Journal of Chinese Cinemas*, February 2024, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17508061.2023.2292462>.

³⁹ Filmportal: *Fern Andra*. https://www.filmportal.de/en/person/fern-andra_ef7842cbc73b335be03053d50b374843, last accessed 04/04/2025.